

The Opportunities of Using a Logistics Service Marketplace to Decrease Emissions of Transport and Logistics Industry

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Abstract. Currently transportation is responsible for 25% of total greenhouse gas emissions in Europe. This share is set to rise, as many other industries have larger incentives to reduce emissions. Thus far, a majority of companies have concentrated on their primary emissions (Scope 1) and the emissions caused by their energy use (Scope 2). Beginning in 2024, incoming EU regulations will demand that large companies report their indirect Scope 3 emissions, and they will gradually expand to include all companies operating within the EU by 2028. The fundamental aim of the regulations is to drive emissions reductions in supply chains. To tackle the challenges posed by this new legislation, this paper takes a closer look at decision-making in transport and logistics service purchasing and considers how the use of a digital marketplace that trades transport and logistics services could improve the emissions transparency in supply chains and steer companies to select less polluting service alternatives. Finally, the paper determines the characteristics for such a marketplace.

Keywords: Marketplace · Logistics service provider · Scope 3 emissions · Sustainable supply chain management · Sustainable transport

1 Introduction and Objectives

Currently transportation is responsible for 25% of total greenhouse gas emissions in Europe. This share is set to rise, as many other industries have larger incentives to reduce emissions. Thus far, a majority of companies have concentrated on their primary emissions (Scope 1) and the emissions caused by their energy use (Scope 2). These are the emissions that companies are currently required to report, and due to public attention, many companies aim to decrease these emissions. However, emissions produced by the supply chain (Scope 3) have rarely been focused on by companies, because there has been no incentive to report these emissions, and many companies are not even aware of them. While firms are more focused on sustainability today, the reality in the logistics industry in general is that most purchasing decisions on transport and logistics services are primarily based on costs. Low energy and low polluting alternatives are only chosen if they do not significantly raise costs.

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Beginning in 2024, incoming EU regulations will demand that large companies report their indirect Scope 3 emissions, and they will gradually expand to include all companies operating within the EU by 2028. This will require companies to measure these emissions. Further public and regulatory pressure to motivate their reduction can also be expected. This progress should change the mindset in the logistics industry from price-driven to emissions-driven. However, the first challenge in this progress is companies' poor awareness of their Scope 3 emissions. Additionally, even if this emissions data is available, it might be too general to make well-informed decisions on emissions reduction efforts. The second challenge is that even if the responsible companies are aware of emissions in their supply chain, they have limited influence on them. IEA (2020) Third, providing sustainable logistics services might be more expensive than doing business as usual, at least in the short term. To create successful business with sustainable logistics services, those sustainable service providers should be easily available, and they should be able to reliably show the emissions produced and the energy used.

To tackle these challenges, this paper takes a closer look at decision-making in transport and logistics service purchasing and considers how the use of a digital marketplace that trades transport and logistics services could improve the emissions transparency in supply chains and steer companies to select less polluting service alternatives. Finally, the paper determines the characteristics for such a marketplace.

2 Theoretical Background

The CDP's Global Supply Chain Report (2023) indicates that upstream Scope 3 emissions are on average 11.4 times greater than Scope 1 and/or 2 emissions. In industries that mainly produce end products for the market, Scope 3 emissions can account for up to 90% of all emissions. Addressing Scope 3 emissions is therefore essential for companies to credibly commit to combating climate change (World Economic Forum (WEF) 2021).

Companies have historically been more interested in the direct environmental impacts of their own operations, paying less attention to the broader effects of their entire supply chain (CDP 2023). It is argued that decarbonizing supply chains could be a crucial factor in the fight against climate change, but this would necessitate a significant structural transformation, involving systematic emissions reduction through controlled transitions (WEF2021).

Major reasons preventing companies from committing to emissions reductions include costs and inadequate regulation. Challenges such as limited sharing of high-quality data, ambiguity surrounding Scope 3 boundaries, and conflicting procurement priorities are viewed as barriers to addressing supply chain emissions (WEF 2021). Scope 3 emissions are often approximations because their calculation relies on various methods, ranging from supplier- or site-specific approaches to average-data or spend-based calculations (Kojo 2023). Limited data transparency, low data quality, and a lack of automated data extraction tools are identified as additional barriers (Kojo 2023).

The complexity and interdependence of numerous factors within supply chains and transportation make it a formidable challenge for researchers to identify innovative

points of intervention that could accelerate a comprehensive shift toward significant decarbonization (Meadows 1997). To address this challenge, there is a growing trend in transportation research that adopts a more holistic perspective, viewing the issue through the lens of socio-technical systems change. Siren (2021) this approach recognizes the need for fundamental changes in both the social and technical structures that currently dominate transportation to align with the evolving environmental requirements (Shankar et al. 2019). Achieving substantial change in such a complex system through top-down policy interventions necessitates a robust bottom-up response (Grin et al. 2010).

From a technical perspective, digital platforms have been one growing solution to engage more closely with different kinds of stakeholders in value chains, business networks, and ecosystems (Shree et al. 2021). A digital platform is an infrastructure supporting interactions and defining governance conditions for the digital ecosystem stakeholders (Hein et al. 2020). Platform ecosystems have been studied extensively, but the understanding of their emergence has received less attention (Pussinen et al. 2023; Valkokari et al. 2022). Our research aims to take the longitudinal approach by observing and understanding the emergence of the ADMIRAL marketplace ecosystem.

3 Methodology

The empirical research design is based on a qualitative case study of a software company, Awake.AI, that is developing a digital marketplace for emissions-aware logistics services in the EU co-funded project ADMIRAL. Awake.AI was founded in 2018 to develop a software platform for digitizing ports and enabling Smart Ports to process remote controlled and autonomous maritime traffic. The project is still in its early phases, having begun in May 2023 and continuing until 2026. Thus, the findings and conclusions presented should be considered as preliminary.

The collaboration between the researchers and Awake.AI on developing the ADMIRAL marketplace has just begun. The aim of the research activities so far has been: 1) to understand the development history and current state of the company and its platform solution, and 2) to start depicting the future functionalities of the marketplace and the overall objectives and approaches for its development. The researchers (3–5 researchers, one acting as the main interviewer and the others supplementing with questions and documenting the interview) have had three focused 1-1,5-h semi-structured interviews with the Vice President of Product from Awake.AI that were documented through video recordings and meeting notes. Furthermore, there have been two project meetings where Awake.AI has presented its development plan to the whole project consortium. The interviewee has also provided researchers with some earlier platform development-related documents. A specific platform canvas was derived from several platform business model canvases to develop a framework to support the depiction of the ADMIRAL business model and analysis of the various factors affecting it.

4 Preliminary Findings - Platform Development

Initially the Awake.AI data platform with Smart Port UI (Smart Port as a Service) focused on enhancing and optimizing the ship-port-land transport part of the logistics chain, e.g., predicting of estimated time of arrival (ETA) and departure (ETD) of a vessel (Fig. 1).

In the beginning, the focus was on ports, which as core actors enable contacts with the most important stakeholders (port authorities, shipping companies, terminal operators, etc.) in terms of port operations, and other ports. The data platform solution contains a web-application and native applications for Android and iOS. In addition, multiple APIs are commercially available. The benefits of the data platform can be seen in the efficiency of operations, the elimination of surprises and delays, as well as the real-time transparency of information. For example, fuel savings are achieved by adjusting the vessel's speed according to optimal port arrival time. In terms of platform development, it has been important to produce functionalities that are easy to deploy and from which users immediately gain personal value.

Recently, Awake.AI has started to build the Awake.AI marketplace on top of the existing data platform. The business logic and scaling of the marketplace is different from that of the data platform. The marketplace facilitates interaction between the stakeholders by enabling service buyers to find and buy items from service providers (physical and digital services and products) via one channel in the context of port and vessel. Furthermore, it enables advertising in the marketplace. Awake.AI as an operator of the marketplace provides rules and guidance to participate in the marketplace. The marketplace has a step-by-step onboarding process and user guidelines as well as an onboarding approval procedure. The Awake.AI marketplace uses Awake.AI's data platform, which provides transparency into data, such as vessel positions and ETA predictions to be utilised in the marketplace. The data platform enriches external data (e.g., weather data, vessel position data, port call data, etc.) with the help of artificial intelligence to create estimates such as vessel ETAs for the marketplace.

In the ADMIRAL project, the multimodal marketplace is built on top of the Awake.AI data platform and marketplace (Fig. 1). The goal of the ADMIRAL project is to expand the current version of the marketplace for multimodality, emissions awareness and optimizing logistics efficiency as well as scale the AI driven trading and routing to multiple logistics chains globally.

From a collaboration point of view, the ADMIRAL marketplace enables a reliable cooperation platform for emissions transparency in logistics. The marketplace connects logistics sellers and buyers, allowing them to easily find, compare, and buy emission-aware multimodal logistics - from door-to-door. The marketplace aims to provide listings of optimal logistics service chains based on a customer's transportation needs as well as facilitate emission-based decision making by providing multimodal logistics emission calculations and comparisons of different logistics chains. Furthermore, the project is also creating the capability for application developers to build their own applications on top of the marketplace platform. Developers can also take a role in where their application(s) feed in data for the marketplace. This is related to, e.g., the launch of the developer portal and other technical and cooperative practices to support participation in the marketplace.

Fig. 1. ADMIRAL marketplace.

5 Conclusions

The importance of emissions reduction in business decision making is increasing, with stricter regulations being one key driver. Meeting the new landscape requirements necessitates the adaptation of technologies such as data platforms to increase transparency on emissions, in addition to social changes in current mindsets and business models. As transportation and logistics services operate in a very dispersed and interconnected business environment, driving change in the industry will be challenging. Platform-based business concepts are potential solutions to connect the stakeholders in this complex environment. The broad scope and complexity of global logistics chains means that there is a slim chance of providing a total solution for emissions-aware logistics information sharing and planning. Rather, the solution should be modular with easy to connect interfaces (APIs) to existing systems as well as new and upcoming systems. This enables the provision of good quality software solutions that are easy to deploy for different customers and can meet their varying needs.

Furthermore, from the point of view of platform ecosystems, longitudinal research on the development and emergence of new platform solutions is needed. Our case study is in its early phase and therefore the findings can only be considered as preliminary. However, the project will continue for two more years providing a unique opportunity to closely follow the development path of an emerging digital logistics platform. Moreover, it provides an opportunity to gain important insights into the complex challenges and solutions of sharing emissions data between a wide variety of logistics sector stakeholders.

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